

PHYSICAL-MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF NA-KMS AND CARBAPOLL BASED GELS

Jurakulov Sanjar Zafarjon Oghly

Asian International University, Senior Lecturer, Uzbekistan

E-mail: juraqulovsanjarzafarjonugli@oxu.uz

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10393950>

Annotation: In the scientific research work, the issue of studying the properties and structure of gels obtained on the basis of sodium-carboxymethylcellulose and carbopol is put forward. Environmentally clean and economically efficient polyelectrolytes produced in our republic on an industrial scale have previously known structures and properties based on sodium-carboxymethylcellulose and carbopol. creation of gels with. X-ray study and analysis of the structure of the gel obtained on the basis of sodium-carboxymethylcellulose and carbapol. Gels (lat. gelo - solidify) are liquid or gaseous mediums with dispersed systems that exhibit some of the properties of solids. As a result of the formation of internal structures between macromolecules of colloidal particles or polymers due to the effect of intermolecular forces, the system has completely lost the property of fluidity, or, in other words, a system. called a gel. Gel has shape retention, strength, plasticity and other properties. These properties in them arise due to the presence of structure-forming species consisting of dispersed phase particles interconnected by intermolecular forces.

Key words: NA-KMS, KRS-5, IR spectra, PK solutions

Introduction: Polysaccharides **are** high-molecular carbohydrates composed of monosaccharide residues. Polysaccharides are one of the main groups of biopolymers widely distributed in animals, plants and microorganisms, they perform various functions in the body. General formula of many common polysaccharides

are considered condensation **polymers** formed from monosaccharides or their derivatives . According to the composition of monosaccharides, polysaccharides are divided into **homopolysaccharides** and **heteropolysaccharides** .

Spectroscopy. The infrared part of electromagnetic spectroscopy is divided into three areas.

1. Near infrared field $0.8 \div 2.5 \text{ m m } 12500 \div 4000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$
2. Mid-infrared area $2.5 \div 50 \text{ m m } 4000 \div 200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$
3. Far infrared field $50 \div 10 \text{ m m } 200 \div 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$

Infrared spectroscopy (IR spectroscopy) is a branch of molecular optical spectroscopy that studies the absorption and reflection spectra of electromagnetic radiation in the IR region. The main characteristics of the IR absorption spectrum: the number of absorption bands in the spectrum, their location is determined by the frequency (or wavelength), the width and shape of the bands, the amount of absorption is determined by the nature (structure), the absorption of the substance depends on the chemical composition of the substance, as well as the substance's total depending on the condition of the plant, temperature, pressure, etc.

IR Spectroscopy IR spectra in the range of $400\text{-}4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$ were recorded on Specord -75 IR (Carl Zeiss) and UR-20 (GDR) spectrophotometers. Samples for IR spectroscopy were prepared in the form of KBr tablets, films on a KRS-5 plate and films with a thickness of $8\text{-}12\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ obtained by the method described above. Films on KRS-5 plates were obtained by evaporating the solvent (water) at room temperature ($22\text{-}24^\circ\text{C}$). Calculation of salt bonds from IR spectra was carried out according to the method described in the work.

The pH indicator of 0.2% solution of K arbopol is equal to 3.5 and its pH

indicator can be controlled in the range from 5 to 10 with the help of neutralizing agents. When carbopol was studied using the IR spectrum, it was found that it contains carboxyl group from 50% to 68.5%. In addition to the carboxyl group, it contains other bands, namely 2960 cm^{-1} , 1720 cm^{-1} , 1455 cm^{-1} , 1415 cm^{-1} , 1250 cm^{-1} , 1175 cm^{-1} , 800 cm^{-1} bands. The most important of these is the band of the carboxyl group at 1720 cm^{-1} [44]. When aqueous solutions of Na-KMS and Carbopol are mixed, water-soluble PK is formed. PKs obtained on the basis of Na-KMS and carbopol and their constituent components were studied using a device consisting of a combination of electrodes "210 Banchtop pH/mV meter". The accuracy level of the measurement results of the device was 0.01 pH indicator. Before measuring these results, the device was adjusted using standard buffer solutions. The process of potentiometric titration

of the prepared PK solutions was measured in a state where the solutions were constantly mixed and the temperature was constant at 22-24 °C. The pH value of the 1% solution of Na-KMS in water is in the range of pH=6.5-7.5, and when it is mixed with the 1% solution of carbapol in a ratio of 1:1, water-soluble polymer composites are formed. It mainly interacts with the hydroxyl group of Na-KMS and the hydroxyl ion of the carboxyl groups of carbapol to form hydrogen bonds. When we mixed solutions of Na-KMS and carbapol, a neutral mixture with a pH value of pH=4 was formed. The resulting mixture is evaporated for two days in the open air at room temperature. A film was formed when the water evaporated. When its water solubility property was checked, it dissolved well and in a short time in water (Table 3.1).

Composite material films with three different pH values of the interpolymer mixture were obtained. IK spectra of the obtained films were studied.

Table 1 I

	pH indicator		
	pH= 4.0	pH=2.91	pH=2.52
Na-KMS - Carbapol	A homogeneous water-soluble film is formed	A partially soluble film is formed in homogeneous water	A homogeneous water-insoluble film with high viscosity is formed

The resulting film was tested for water solubility by placing it in distilled water. In this case, the film did not dissolve in water at all.

Composite material films with three different pH values of the interpolymer mixture were obtained. IK spectra of the obtained films were studied.

2 - table.

Frequency	Na-KMS + Carbapol		
	pH=4	pH=2.91	pH=2.52
3000	3382.68	0	0
2500	2924.07	2924.63	2926.89
	0	2650.97	2641.81
2000	0	0	0

X-ray analysis of film with pH=2.52.

Conclusion: As can be seen from these X-ray structures, some degree of peaks were formed when X-rays were sent to each film. X-ray and IK-spectra of the composite plonyankas were taken in order to study the structural properties of the composite plonyankas.

References:

1. Jurakulov, SZ (2023). NUCLEAR ENERGY. Educational Research in Universal Sciences , 2 (10), 514-518.
2. Oghly, JSZ (2023). PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF POLYMER COMPOSITES. American Journal of Applied Science and Technology , 3 (10), 25-33.
3. Oghly, JSZ (2023). THE RELATIONSHIP OF PHYSICS AND ART IN ARISTOTLE'S SYSTEM. International Journal of Pedagogics , 3 (11), 67-73.
4. Oghly, JSZ (2023). BASIC PHILOSOPHICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL IDEAS IN THE EVOLUTION OF PHYSICAL SCIENCES. Gospodarka i Innowacje. , 41 , 233-241.
5. ugli Jurakulov, SZ (2023). STRATEGIES FOR SUCCESSFUL PHYSICS EDUCATION. Educational Research in Universal Sciences , 2 (14), 46-48.
6. Oghly, JSZ (2023). A Japanese approach to in-service training and professional development of science and physics teachers in Japan. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157) , 1 (9), 167-173.
7. Oghly, JSZ (2023). STRATEGIES FOR SUCCESSFUL LEARNING IN PHYSICS. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157) , 1 (9), 312-318.
8. Jurakulov, SZO, & Turdiboyev, H. (2023). RELATIONSHIPS OF PHYSICS WITH ART IN THE FIELD OF EDUCATION. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 144-147.
9. Jurakulov, SZO, & Turdiboyev, K. (2023). STUDYING PHYSICS USING A COMPUTER. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 148-151.
10. Jurakulov, SZO, & Nurboyev, O. (2023). LEVEL AND POSITION IN THE EDUCATIONAL FIELD OF PHYSICS. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 157-161.

11. Jurakulov, SZO, & Nurboyev, O. (2023). THE MAIN SIGNIFICANCE OF THE DEPARTMENTS OF PHYSICS IN THE DEVELOPMENT. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 162–167.
12. Jurakulov, SZO, & Nurboyev, O. (2023). RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN THE DIRECTIONS OF FINANCE AND PHYSICAL SCIENCE. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 168–172.
13. Jurakulov, SZO, & Hamidov, E. (2023). PROPERTIES AND CHARACTERISTICS OF NUCLEAR ENERGY. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 182–186.
14. Jurakulov, SZO, & Turdiboyev, H. (2023). ADVANCED STRATEGIES FOR LEARNING PHYSICS. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(33), 152–156.
15. Oghly, JSZ (2023). New Computer-Assisted Approaches to Teaching Physics. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1 (10), 173-177.
16. Oghly, JSZ (2023). A Current Perspective on the Relationship between Economics and Physics. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1 (10), 154-159.
17. Sharipova, M. P. L. (2023). CAPUTA MA'NOSIDA KASR TARTIBLI HOSILALAR VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 360-365.
18. Sharipova, M. P. (2023). MAXSUS SOHALARDA KARLEMAN MATRITSASI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(10), 137-141.
19. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). APPROXIMATION OF FUNCTIONS WITH COEFFICIENTS. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 135–138.
20. Madina Polatovna Sharipova. (2023). Applications of the double integral to mechanical problems. International journal of sciearchers, 2(2), 101-103.
21. Sharipova, M. P. L. (2023). FINDING THE MAXIMUM AND MINIMUM VALUE OF A FUNCTION ON A SEGMENT. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 245-248.
22. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). KASR TARTIBLI HOSILA TUSHUNCHASI. SCHOLAR, 1(31), 263-269.
23. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). RIMAN-LUIVILL KASR TARTIBLI INTEGRALI VA HOSILASIGA OID AYRIM MASALALARNING ISHLANISHI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(12), 216-220.
24. qizi Latipova, S. S. (2023). MITTAG–LIFFLER FUNKSIYASI VA UNI HISOBLASH USULLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(9), 238-244.

25. Shahnoza, L. (2023, March). KASR TARTIBLI TENGLAMALARDA MANBA VA BOSHLANG'ICH FUNKSIYANI ANIQLASH BO'YICHA TESKARI MASALALAR. In "Conference on Universal Science Research 2023" (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 8-10).
26. Axmedova, Z. I. (2023). LMS TIZIMIDA INTERAKTIV ELEMENTLARNI YARATISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(11), 368-372.
27. Ikromovna, A. Z. (2023). USING THE USEFUL ASPECTS OF THE MOODLE SYSTEM AND ITS POSSIBILITIES. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 201-205.
28. Axmedova, Z. (2023). MOODLE TIZIMI VA UNING IMKONIYATLARI. Development and innovations in science, 2(11), 29-35.
29. Zulxumor, A. (2022). IMPLEMENTATION OF INTERACTIVE COURSES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. ILMIY TADQIQOT VA INNOVATSIYA, 1(6), 128-132.
30. Муродов, О. Т. (2023). РАЗРАБОТКА АВТОМАТИЗИРОВАННОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ТЕМПЕРАТУРЫ И ВЛАЖНОСТИ В ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННЫХ КОМНАТ. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(26), 91-95.
31. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). ZAMONAVIY TA'LIMDA AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARI VA ULARNI QO'LLASH USUL VA VOSITALARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(10), 481-486.
32. Murodov, O. T. R. (2023). INFORMATIKA DARSLARINI TASHKIL ETISHDA INNOVATSION USULLARDAN FOYDALANISH. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(32), 194-201
33. qizi Sharopova, M. M. (2023). RSA VA EL-GAMAL OCHIQ KALITLI SHIFRLASH ALGORITMI ASOSIDA ELEKTRON RAQMLI IMZOLARI. RSA OCHIQ KALITLI SHIFRLASH ALGORITMI ASOSIDAGI ELEKTRON RAQAMLI IMZO. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(10), 316-319